

Standard Analysis ANSI/ISA-S5.1 (R-2009)

*Instrumentation Symbols and Identification
for Industrial Process Control*

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Abstract

This document is an integral part of a series of technical texts aimed at supporting and fostering the development of instrumentation and control engineering practice. Its primary objective is to present the most relevant aspects of the *ISA-5.1* standard (*Instrumentation Symbols and Identification*), oriented toward the identification and graphical symbology of industrial instrumentation. This standard is designed to be applied throughout the complete life cycle of an industrial plant: from engineering design and construction, through commissioning, to shutdown or end of useful life, thereby ensuring a traceable record of every instrument through datasheets, calibration records, maintenance logs and operational documentation.

This version incorporates a rigorous foundation of the relationship between the *Work Break-down Structure* (WBS) and the construction of the instrument identification code (*TAG*) according to ISA-5.1, illustrated through a copper concentrator plant example encompassing crushing, stockpiling and transport, grinding and flotation stages. Additionally, the functional identification rules, graphical representation of lines and instruments in *P&ID* documents, and the most commonly used representation cases in instrumentation and process control engineering are described.

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Motivation

The Chilean mining and industrial sector hosts some of the most complex engineering projects in the world. World-class operations such as those of *Codelco*, *Anglo American*, *Collahuasi*, *Antamina* and *Chinalco*, among others, demand technical documentation that is **unambiguous, traceable and universal**: a necessary condition for the correct execution of capital projects, the safe operation of plants and their maintenance over decades of useful life.

In this context, the **Piping and Instrumentation Diagram** (*P&ID*) constitutes the highest-information engineering document in the Instrumentation and Control (I&C) discipline. It describes, in symbolic and coded form, the entirety of the measurement, control and actuation equipment of an industrial process, together with its interconnections and functional logic. The *P&ID* accompanies the plant throughout its entire life cycle, from conceptual engineering to decommissioning.

However, practical experience in *EPCM* (*Engineering, Procurement, Construction & Management*) projects in the Chilean mining-metallurgical sector reveals a recurring training gap: the preparation and interpretation of *P&ID* documents without a solid command of the governing standard, leading to identification inconsistencies, loss of documentary traceability and conflicts during construction and commissioning. This situation is compounded when different engineering disciplines use disparate coding criteria within the same project.

This article addresses that need by providing a rigorous technical reference, on the application of the **ANSI/ISA-5.1 (R-2009)** standard, with emphasis on the structuring criteria that ensure traceability throughout the plant life cycle.

1 Introduction

1.1 Historical context and normative scope

The *International Society of Automation* (ISA), founded in 1945 in Pittsburgh, USA, develops and publishes the most globally adopted international standards for automation and industrial instrumentation. The **ISA-5** family groups the standards for instrumentation identification and graphical representation (Table 1).

Table 1: ISA-5 family of standards for instrumentation and process control

Standard	Scope
ISA-5.1	Instrumentation Symbols and Identification. Covers P&ID documents and instrument loop identification. <i>Subject of this document.</i>
ISA-5.2	Binary Logic Diagrams for Process Operations.
ISA-5.3	Graphic Symbols for Distributed Control/Shared Display Instrumentation, Logic and Computer Systems.
ISA-5.4	Instrument Loop Diagrams. Direct complement to ISA-5.1: details the loop at the wiring, terminal, model and calibration level. <i>Referenced in this document.</i>
ISA-5.5	Graphic Symbols for Process Displays.

Scope of this document

This article covers the **ISA-5.1 (R-2009)** standard in depth, which governs the *P&ID* and instrument identification. **ISA-5.4** is referenced as the direct complement (*Loop Diagrams*) in detailed engineering. Standards ISA-5.2, 5.3 and 5.5 are outside the scope of this work.

The original version of the standard dates from **1984**; its current revision is the **R-2009** publication, also adopted by **ANSI** (*American National Standards Institute*). Concurrently, the European equivalent standard is **DIN 19227** (*Deutsches Institut für Normung*), prevalent in projects of European origin. In Chile, ISA-5.1 is **contractually mandated** in practically all EPCM-type projects in the mining, metallurgical and hydrocarbon industries.

1.2 The *P&ID* and the plant life cycle

The *P&ID* is not merely an engineering drawing: it is the document upon which all life-cycle information for each instrument is articulated. ISA-5.1 establishes that the identification code (*tag number*) generated under its criteria must accompany the instrument throughout **all stages of the life cycle**, uniquely linking the following documents:

- Technical datasheet and instrument specification.
- Calibration record and maintenance log.
- Material certificates and manufacturer documents.
- Installation and wiring drawings and Loop Diagrams (ISA-5.4).
- Failure, repair and replacement records.
- Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) and safety procedures.
- Asset management system records (SAP-PM, Maximo, etc.).

1.3 The WBS as the structural foundation of the ISA-5.1 TAG

1.3.1 What is the WBS and why is it essential in instrumentation?

One of the most frequent deficiencies in industrial projects is the *ad-hoc* assignment of area codes and loop numbers, without a systematic criterion to guarantee uniqueness and documentary coherence. This deficiency has an explicit solution within the ISA-5.1 standard itself: the binding of the TAG area field to the **Work Breakdown Structure** (WBS).

Definition — Work Breakdown Structure (WBS)

The WBS is a hierarchical decomposition oriented toward **deliverables** of the total work that must be executed by the project team in order to achieve the defined objectives (PMI, PMBOK 7). **It is not an activity list**: it is a structure that defines *what* must be produced, organized in progressively finer levels of detail.

Typical hierarchy in an industrial project:

Project → Functional area → Sub-area / System → Work package

The WBS is organized by **deliverables**, not by disciplines or activities. Its output is a hierarchical tree of alphanumeric codes that delimits the total project scope into verifiable units.

The connection between the WBS and the ISA-5.1 TAG is not conceptual or optional: it is **structural and direct**. The AAA field (area code) of the TAG is derived from the WBS nodes defined in the early project stages (*FEED* or basic engineering). Without a properly structured and approved WBS, instrument identification lacks a hierarchical reference, invariably producing duplicate tags, inter-discipline inconsistencies and loss of documentary traceability.

1.3.2 Applied example: Copper Concentrator Plant

To illustrate the WBS ↔ ISA-5.1 TAG relationship concretely, the typical process of a **copper concentrator plant** is used, comprising crushing, stockpiling and transport, grinding and flotation stages.

Process flowchart — Copper Concentrator Plant Figure 1 shows the process flow of the concentrator plant from primary crushing through to the production of copper concentrate, identifying the WBS area of each stage.

Figure 1: Process flowchart — Copper Concentrator Plant with WBS area identification and ISA-5.1 TAG examples

Hierarchical WBS — Copper Concentrator Plant Figure 2 shows the complete WBS tree of the concentrator plant down to level 3 (sub-area / system), which is the level from which the area codes of the ISA-5.1 TAG are generated.

Figure 2: Hierarchical WBS — Copper Concentrator Plant (Levels 0–3). Level-3 codes (WBS 1xx, 2xx, 3xx, 4xx) correspond to the AAA field of the ISA-5.1 TAG.

1.3.3 Direct correspondence between WBS and TAG structure

Revisiting the TAG structure defined in ISA-5.1, Figure 3 decomposes its fields and establishes an explicit link to the WBS.

Figure 3: ISA-5.1 TAG structure with origin of each field and example applied to the SAG Mill area (WBS 310) of the concentrator plant

Table 2 illustrates the complete correspondence between the WBS nodes of the concentrator plant and the resulting ISA-5.1 TAGs.

Table 2: WBS ↔ ISA-5.1 TAG correspondence — Copper Concentrator Plant

WBS L1	WBS L2 (area)	WBS L3 (sub-area)	Code	Resulting TAG example
Concentrator Plant	Crushing	Primary Crushing	110	110-WI-1001 (<i>Belt weighfeeder</i>)
	Crushing	Sec./Tert. Crushing	120/130	120-ZT-1201 (<i>Crusher position</i>)
	Stockpile & Transp.	Coarse Ore Stockpile	210	210-LT-2001 (<i>Stockpile level</i>)
	Stockpile & Transp.	Conveyor Belt	220	220-WI-2201 (<i>Belt scale</i>)
	Grinding	SAG Mill	310	310-PT-3001 (<i>SAG discharge pressure</i>)
	Grinding	Ball Mill	320	320-FT-3201 (<i>Discharge slurry flow</i>)
	Grinding	Cyclone Classification	330	330-FT-3301 (<i>Cyclone feed flow</i>)
	Flotation	Rougher Flotation	410	410-AT-4101 (<i>Slurry density analysis</i>)
	Flotation	Scavenger Flotation	420	420-LT-4201 (<i>Cell level</i>)
	Flotation	Cleaner Flotation	430	430-AT-4301 (<i>%Cu concentrate analysis</i>)

Example — Instrument redundancy and suffix in WBS context

In the Rougher Flotation area (WBS 410), if two redundant density transmitters are installed at the head-cell feed, both belong to the same loop (4105) and are distinguished by suffix:

410-DT-4105A and 410-DT-4105B

The suffix A/B denotes functional redundancy within the same loop and the same WBS area. If the transmitters were located in different WBS areas, the area code would already differentiate them and no suffix would be required to guarantee TAG uniqueness across the plant (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Flotation cell feed with redundant density transmitters

1.3.4 Consequences of not linking the TAG to the WBS

The absence of a WBS as the basis for ISA-5.1 identification produces concrete problems, recurring across industrial projects:

- **Duplicate TAGs:** Two instruments in physically distinct areas receive the same code, creating conflicts in the instrument index and in the control system database.
- **Loss of traceability:** Without a coherent area criterion, the association between the instrument tag and its related documents (datasheet, loop, procedures) breaks down under engineering changes — a routine occurrence in EPCM projects.
- **Inter-discipline conflicts:** Process, electrical, civil and structural disciplines all use the same WBS as the basis for their own documents. If the I&C WBS diverges, the project documentary integration is fractured.
- **CMMS/EAM system issues:** Systems such as SAP-PM or IBM Maximo use the ISA-5.1 tag as the primary key of each physical asset. A poorly structured tag propagates errors throughout the asset management system for the entire operational life of the plant (typically 20–40 years in mining).

- **Recoding during construction:** Late definition of the WBS forces instrument recoding during construction, with a direct impact on cost, schedule and the integrity of the project document management system.

1.3.5 The WBS as an early-stage reference document in the project

A critical aspect that ISA-5.1 alone cannot resolve is the **timing** at which the WBS must be defined. Practice in Chilean EPCM projects establishes that the WBS must be approved during the **FEED** (*Front End Engineering Design*) stage, before detailed engineering commences.

Application criterion in EPCM project engineering

The I&C discipline WBS must be developed in coordination with the process area, so that the WBS area codes align with those defined in the process *P&IDs*. This early coordination is the only way to ensure that the ISA-5.1 TAG fulfils its role as a unique and traceable identifier throughout the entire plant life cycle.

In large-scale Chilean projects, the FEED-approved WBS is a contractually binding management document; any subsequent modification requires formal Change Management with assessed impact on cost and schedule.

1.3.6 Relationship between WBS, ISA-5.1 and ISA-5.4

The **ISA-5.4** standard defines the *Instrument Loop Diagram*, which complements the *P&ID* with the wiring, terminal, power supply and calibration detail for each instrument. The connection between both documents is made through the **ISA-5.1 TAG**: the loop documented in ISA-5.4 carries the same loop number (CCCC) and area code (AAA) as the instruments in the *P&ID*.

The WBS thus underpins a **coherent documentary chain**:

WBS $\xrightarrow{\text{defines}}$ ISA-5.1 TAG $\xrightarrow{\text{structures}}$ P&ID (ISA-5.1) $\xrightarrow{\text{details}}$ Loop Diagram (ISA-5.4)

2 ISA-5.1 Standard — *Instrumentation Symbols and Identification*

This standard, as its name indicates, is not mandatorily applicable in the development of instrumentation and control engineering; however, it has become one of the most widely used standards internationally, alongside **DIN 19227** (*Deutsches Institut für Normung*) in the process industries.

The application of this standard is of high importance throughout the plant life cycle, given that the outcome of the identification and graphical designation process will accompany the instrument at all its stages: engineering design, construction, commissioning and service through to plant closure or decommissioning of the service in which the instrument has been incorporated. Its use guarantees the **traceability** of the information associated with each instrument (datasheets, calibration, maintenance, failure and repair records, among others).

The ISA standard establishes that an instrument's identification or **TAG** shall be an alphanumeric code composed of information fields with meaning associated with the location, function, loop and

measured variable of the instrument being identified.

2.1 Application of the standard

In applying the standard, the **TAG** is defined as the concatenated set of information fields of the instrument being identified (Table 3).

The following criteria must be observed:

- The meanings of the identifying letters must be in **English**, owing to the international adoption of this standard across virtually all industrial processes worldwide.
- The process and sub-process area designation must be defined systematically from the WBS. These initial digits must be established in the early stages of the project (see Section 1.3).
- Each instrument in a system must be identified with a unique alphanumeric code (*tag number*) containing the loop number to which it belongs (Table 3).

Table 3: Example of application of TAG information fields

Measured variable	Primary function	Secondary function	Loop No.	Meaning
P	I	T	103	Instrument identification
P			103	Loop identification
			103	Loop number
PIT	I	T		Functional identification
P				First letter
	I	T		Succeeding letters

- The maximum number of functional letters shall not exceed **4 characters**.
- In the case of multi-function elements, these may be shown with combined circles specifying the additional function (e.g., *differential pressure indicating transmitter with high switch*).

Figure 5: Example of multi-function tag application

- For loop identification, a numeric code shall be used. Where more than two instruments perform the same function (e.g., redundant temperature transmitters), they may share the same loop number and carry an additional suffix (a letter or number separated by a hyphen).
- Instruments with auxiliary elements (diaphragm seals, air-filter regulators, isolation valves) may incorporate those elements using a suffix or the second letter **X**. For example, the 3 valves of the *manifold* of a volumetric flowmeter: FX-100A, FX-100B and FX-100C.

2.2 TAG information fields

The composition of a TAG is defined according to Table 4.

Table 4: ISA-5.1 TAG information fields

TAG	AREA	FUNCTIONAL ID	LOOP	SUFFIX
AAA-BBBB-CCCCD	AAA	BBBB	CCCC	D

- **AAA:** Functional area of the process where the instrument or final control element is located. Derived from the WBS level-3 node.
- **BBBB:** Functional identifier. Contains the measured variable, primary function and secondary function information: the code that defines the measurement variable, instrument type and its function within the control loop.
- **CCCC:** Loop number. Identifies the family to which the instrument belongs; it is recommended to be unique within the plant.
- **D:** Suffix. Used for instruments within the same loop performing the same function (e.g., two temperature sensors feeding the same transmitter: TE-100A and TE-100B).

2.3 Identifying letters in the TAG

Table 5 presents the letter code with the meanings of letters as first letter (measured variable or modifier) and succeeding letters (passive reading, output function, modifier).

Table 5: Identifying letter definition table — ISA-5.1 (Part 1)

First Letter			Succeeding Letters		
	Measured or initiating variable	Modifier	Readout or passive function	Output function	Modifier
A	Analysis (5, 19)		Alarm		
B	Burner, combustion		User's choice (1)	User's choice (1)	User's choice (1)
C	User's choice (1)			Control (13)	
D	User's choice (1)	Differential (4)			
E	Voltage (EMF)		Sensor (primary element)		
F	Flow rate	Ratio (4)			
G	User's choice (1)		Glass, viewing device (9)		
H	Hand				High (7,15,16)
I	Current (electrical)		Indicate (10)		
J	Power	Scan (7)			
K	Time, time schedule	Time rate of change (4)		Control station	
L	Level		Light (11)		Low (7,15,16)
M	User's choice (1)	Momentary (4)			Middle, intermediate (7,15)

Table 6: Identifying letter definition table — ISA-5.1 (Part 2)

First Letter			Succeeding Letters		
	Measured or initiating variable	Modifier	Readout or passive function	Output function	Modifier
N	User's choice (1)		User's choice (1)	User's choice (1)	User's choice (1)
O	User's choice (1)		Orifice, restriction		
P	Pressure, vacuum		Point (test connection)		
Q	Quantity	Integrate, totalize (4)			
R	Radiation		Record (17)		
S	Speed, frequency	Safety (8)		Switch (13)	
T	Temperature			Transmit (18)	
U	Multivariable (6)		Multifunction (12)	Multifunction (12)	Multifunction (12)
V	Vibration, mechanical analysis (19)			Valve, damper, louver (13)	
W	Weight, force		Well, probe		
X	Unclassified (2)	X-axis	Unclassified (2)	Unclassified (2)	Unclassified (2)
Y	Event, state or presence	Y-axis		Relay, compute, convert (13,14,18)	
Z	Position, dimension	Z-axis		Driver, actuator, unclassified final control element	

With respect to Tables 5 and 6, the numbered notes mean the following:

- (1) To cover non-standard functions and elements, certain letters are available for user's choice. The letter "X" as a first letter may mean "unclassified variable"; as a succeeding letter it may mean "unclassified element" (components of a manifold or of an instrument air-filter regulator).
- (2) For the letter "X" it is recommended that its designation and meaning within a given project be defined only once and not assigned different meanings.
- (3) The grammatical forms of the functions may be modified as required (e.g., "Record", "Recording").
- (4) Certain letters such as "D" may mean, as a succeeding letter, a measured variable; for example, differential pressure may be designated "PD". Similarly, the letter "F" as a succeeding letter means "Ratio".
- (5) The letter "A" may be used for almost all methods of analysis. **Note:** In ISA-5.1, conductivity is frequently assigned to "Q" (quantity/quality) or under "A" (process analysis); the use of "C" for conductivity is a project convention, not an explicit normative definition of the standard.
- (6) Use of the letter "U" is suggested for multivariable measurement, control and actuation elements (e.g., multivariable indicators on an HMI).
- (7) Use of the high/low qualifiers high, low, high-high, low-low is always recommended, using the letter combinations "H", "L", "HH", "LL" respectively.
- (8) The letter "S" as a succeeding letter means "Safety". Example: a standard pressure regulating valve is designated "PCV"; if it serves to regulate variables at critical or safety levels, it shall be designated "PSV". Belt-conveyor safety switches of the Pull-Cord type shall be designated "HSS".
- (9) The letter "G" is used for local visual indication elements (Level Glass "LG" or tank sight glasses).
- (10) The letter "I" for indication refers to the readout of a real analog or digital process measurement.
- (11) A pilot light that is part of a control loop shall be designated by a first letter followed by the succeeding letter "L". For example, a pilot light indicating high level of a tank: "LLH". The designation "XL" shall not be used for motor pilot lights.
- (12) Use of the letter "U" is recommended to indicate any multivariable instrument or function.
- (13) A "switch" is defined as any element that performs a switching action to activate, in discrete fashion, other elements, states or signals: On-Off controls, relays, contactors, mechanical safety switches, discrete transducers.
- (14) Associated "Y" functions shall be defined by a note or outside the instrument symbol.
- (15) The terms high, low, high-high, low-low shall correspond to values of the measured variable, not of the signal.

- (16) The terms high and low, when applied to valves or other opening/closing devices: “high” indicates the valve is at or approaching the fully open position; “low” indicates it is at or approaching the fully closed position.
- (17) The word “record” shall be used for any form of process information storage, in any medium.
- (18) The term “transmitter” applies to an instrument that senses a process signal through a sensor and transmits it in accordance with a predetermined function of the process variable, as a normalized instrument output signal (pneumatic, electronic or digital). A “converter” receives an instrument signal and converts it to another form (e.g., receives 0.2 to 1 bar and converts to 4–20 mA).
- (19) The letter “V” is used for mechanical vibration analysis; the letter “A” is used for chemical process analysis in general.

3 Graphical Description of Instrumentation

These criteria aim to describe, in a symbolic and concise manner, the main characteristics of instruments: their function, interconnections and role in a given process. They also allow the representation of the instrument’s location and interaction both within the specific process and throughout the plant in general, and can even indicate whether the instrument generates alarms or provides indications to the operator.

3.1 Physical location of the instrument in the graphical symbol

One of the most relevant aspects of ISA-5.1 that complements the functional identification is the **indication of the physical location** of the instrument. This is expressed through the type of horizontal line inside the circle (or its absence), as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Representation of the physical location of the instrument through the type of horizontal line in the ISA-5.1 graphical symbol

Fundamental criterion frequently omitted

The physical location of the instrument, indicated by the type of interior line of the symbol, is critical information for construction, commissioning and operations teams. Its omission from the *P&ID* is a common error that creates ambiguity during installation and in the management of instrument access during plant operation.

3.2 Graphical lines

The basic graphical designation begins with the designation of lines, connections and signals of instruments and systems (Table 7).

Table 7: Graphical representation of lines, signals and connections of instruments and systems

Líneas Gráficas	Nombre
	Conexión a proceso
	Conexión o línea neumática
	Señal eléctrica
	Conexión hidráulica
	Conexión tipo capilar
	Señal electromagnética guiada
	Señal electromagnética no guiada Señal de comunicación inalámbrica
	Link de datos
	Link de datos
	Link de datos sistema bus

The following designations can be identified in Table 7:

Process connection: Covers all connections between process lines (fluid piping) and process equipment (tanks, pumps, conveyor belts). This line may always be interrupted by piping elements such as isolation valves, as shown in Figure 7, where the level measurement (LT-101) of “Tank 1” by hydrostatic pressure is illustrated.

Pneumatic connection or line: Shows mechanical connections through *Tubing*¹ or small-bore piping, generally used for instrument air supply to actuators (control valves, pneumatic pumps, solenoid valves) or service air (plant air for cleaning or pneumatic tooling).

Electrical signal: Represents the full range of electrical signals: 4–20 mA instrumentation signals, AC/DC instrument power supply lines, motor control signals.

¹Tubing with diameters between 1/8” and 3/4” for working pressures typically around 10 PSIG.

Figure 7: P&ID excerpt: level measurement by hydrostatic pressure

Hydraulic connection: Represents hydraulic power supply to actuators such as hydraulic cylinders, hydraulic valves and hydraulic motors.

Capillary tubing: A very narrow fluid conduit of small circular cross-section, used to transmit pressure from the process to the measuring instrument (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Pressure gauge with diaphragm seal and capillary tubing

Guided electromagnetic signal: Electromagnetic spectrum signals (light, radiofrequency) guided to the measurement point through wave guides such as fiber optic cables or tubular RF wave guides (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Wave guide application for level measurement in a closed tank

Non-guided electromagnetic signal: Acoustic or mechanical signals such as ultrasound, applied in level measurement of tanks open to atmosphere, as well as wireless industrial communication signals (Figure 10).

Figure 10: *WirelessHART* wireless communications architecture

Data link: At least three types are distinguished: (a) **lines with open circles:** software or inter-system data links; (b) **lines with filled circles or open diamonds:** instrumentation field buses (*Foundation Fieldbus, Profibus PA, ProfiNet*, among others) (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Typical *Foundation Fieldbus* field bus architecture

3.3 Graphical representation of instruments and functions

A fundamental aspect of the standard is the graphical description of field instruments, final control elements, distributed control systems, local controllers and hard-wired logic. With a small set of symbols, complex systems must be represented in a simple language that contains sufficient information to understand the operation of an industrial process.

3.3.1 Application of Identification and Symbols

The information fields convey the instrument's function, its location in the functional area and its loop membership. The distribution of these fields in the graphical representation is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Information fields and ISA-5.1 graphical symbol

The upper part of the field corresponds to the functional identification (XXX). In the lower part, the code begins with the functional area (ZZZ) derived from the WBS, followed by the loop number ($YYYY$). The suffix (A) differentiates redundant instruments within the same loop (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Redundant temperature measurement on cooling water at a heat exchanger

Regarding the instrument and function symbology (Table 8):

- **Circles:** Designate field instruments, whether discrete (switches) or continuous (transmitters, positioners). These elements are in direct contact with the physical variables being measured or manipulated.
- **Squares with inscribed circle:** Distributed control (DCS) elements: operator indication, controllers, alarms, scaling, discrete action generation, upper and lower limits for a continuous variable, calculation functions.
- **Squares with inscribed diamond:** Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs), considered local controllers for a specific piece of equipment or sub-process.
- **Hexagons:** Physical computers or specific calculation functions (square-root extractors, compensated flow computers), generally panel- or cabinet-mounted.

Table 8: Graphical representation of instruments and functions (ISA-5.1)

No.	HMI, Sistema Distribuido		C Computa. o Software (4)	D Instrumento Discreto o de Campo (5)	Ubicación y Accesibilidad(6)
	A	B			
	Sistema de Control de Procesos (2)	Sistema de Control Local o de Seguridad (3)			
1		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ubicado en terreno. • No montado en panel o gabinete. cabinet, • Visible en terreno • Normalmente accesible al operador. 			
2		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ubicado en panel central o en consola. • Visible en panel principal o HMI. • Normalmente accesible al operador. (Software y hardware) 			
3		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ubicado en la parte trasera del panel principal. • No visible en la parte frontal del panel o consola (HMI). • Normalmente no es accesible para el operador en la consola. 			
4		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ubicado en o en frente del panel o consola secundaria o local. • Visible en la parte frontal del panel o en la pantalla de video. • Normalmente accesible para el operador desde el panel frontal o la consola. 			
5		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ubicado en la parte posterior del panel secundario o local. • Ubicado en gabinete de campo. • No visible en la parte frontal del panel o en la pantalla de video. • Normalmente no es accesible para el operador en el panel o la consola. 			

3.3.2 Representation of the most common and special cases

- **Circle to square with inscribed circle (instrument → DCS function):** The normalized instrument output (4–20 mA or dry contact) is connected to the control system to establish a discrete function (alarm, status indication) or to perform the scaling of continuous signals. From the programming standpoint, this is where the main variable (*float*) is generated, feeding other subroutines (Table 9).

Table 9: Case summary: physical instrument and DCS function

Location: Field	Location: Control System
Element: Instrument	Element: Function
Process variable measurement	Connection to control system (signal digitization via ADC)
Transmission of measurement as normalized signal (e.g.: 4–20 mA)	Input signal scaling (mapping of normalized signal to engineering variable)
	Operator indication on HMI
	Variable available in software for other routines or functions (alarms)

- **Square to square (function → function):** Establishes the data transfer between software function elements: controller output to a variable frequency drive, feeding a variable to a subroutine, etc. The representation order must always start from the block that generates the signal (Table 10).

Table 10: Case summary: function–function

Location: Control System	Location: Control System
Element: Function	Element: Function
Scaled continuous variable. Represents level $L(t)$	Scaled variable is taken (represents $L(t)$)
Block performs previously described functions	Variable is bounded to a discrete point $LAH = x, \forall x \in L(t)$
	Operator indication on HMI

- **Instrument–function *Interlock*:** The interlock is an algorithm that compares measured process variables against permissible upper and lower limits; if any limit is exceeded, it executes a direct action on final control elements (VFDs, valves, etc.). Informatics analogy: “non-maskable interrupt” — a subroutine of the highest priority in the program (Table 11).

Table 11: Case summary: function–*Interlock*

Location: Control System	Location: Control System
Element: Function	Element: Function
Alarm setpoint selection $LAH = x$	Compares input against upper and lower limits
Block performs previously described tasks	Executes direct action on final control element
	Operator indication on HMI / Alarms

- **Instrument and/or function to *Hardwired Interlock*:** Actuation logic based exclusively on electromechanical elements (relays, contactors), where “dry contacts” are the channels

for transmitting discrete states. Example: emergency stop actuation or motor pushbutton stations (Table 12).

Table 12: Case summary: *Hardwired Interlock*

Location: Field	Location: Control System
Element: Pushbutton “Start/Stop”	Element: Hard-wired Interlock
Transmits Start/Stop state	Energizes (wets) pushbutton contact
Normally-Open / Normally-Closed dry contact	Through electromechanical switching and different states or conditions, generates the interlock output action (Start/Stop)
	Executes command and validates whether it has been performed